

ABSTRACT

Occupational health and safety has continued to remain outside mainstream organisational and management practices while many countries especially in the developing world do not give much attention to health and safety issues and regulatory systems. Therefore, the objective of this research is to assess the leadership responsibility in health and safety, level of safety procedures in its organisations, level of health and safety training given to employees, management commitment to health and safety practices and the effect of health and safety on performance of organisation.

To achieve these objectives, a cross-sectional design type was employed using both descriptive and exploratory design. Stratified and simple random sampling techniques were adopted to collect primary data from three manufacturing companies (Ghana Port and Harbours Authority, NESTLE, and GHACEM) in Tema of the Greater Accra Region of Ghana using survey questionnaires. One hundred and thirty-six respondents correctly filled the survey questionnaires and were processed for results and discussions.

The results showed that majority of the respondents strongly agreed that leadership provide excellent and well documented health and safety policies, and consider health and safety as shared responsibility. Also, on safety procedures, majority of the respondents generally agreed that employees followed safety procedures in their workplace. On the contrary, majority of the respondents generally disagreed that employees always report safety accidents. On management commitment to health and safety, majority of the respondents expressed that management are committed to health and

safety policies. However, it was observed that management do not always request for feedback on safety training and not involving employees in safety planning. On safety and performance issues, majority of the respondents strongly disagreed that organisation is experiencing high absenteeism, interruption in operations due to health and safety issues in the organisations.

In conclusion, these organisations show high leadership and management committed to health and safety practices, employees follow due processes in health and safety standards. However, the level of employees' involvement in reviewing safety issues and requesting for feedback on safety training is important to continuing adhering to safety standard and improving organisations' safety practices and overall performance.

It is therefore recommended that management should improve employees' involvement in safety issues, feedback on training and enhance employees' ability to report all accidents to ensure that safety standards are continuously improved.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Background to the study

Occupational health and safety practices have generally been given little research attention. As a result, occupational health and safety has continued to remain outside mainstream organisational and management researches (Barling et al. 2002). Most countries and industries scarcely recognize occupational health and safety practices as a crucial determinant of national development. Therefore, mainstreaming occupational health and safety into national agenda becomes an important consideration for not only developed countries but also for the developing countries as well (Katsoulakos & Katsoulacos, 2007). Apparently, less than one percent of organisational and national researches focus on issues concerning occupational health and safety practices (Barling & Zacharatos, 2000). Apart from little research attention on occupational health and safety issues in general, there is also an acute lack of literature on these matters. Particularly, most African countries are struggling with occupational health and safety practices as few attempts from the industries and the governments are notable (Meredith, 1986; Regional Committee for Africa Report, 2004).

According to Milkovich and Boudreau (1991) safety hazards are those aspects of the work environment, which have the potential for immediate and sometimes violent harm to an employee. Examples are loss of hearing or eyesight, cuts, sprains, bruises and broken bones, burns and electric shocks. Health hazards are those aspects of work environment that slowly and

cumulatively lead to deterioration of an employee's health. Typical causes include physical and biological hazards, toxic and cancer-causing dusts and chemicals, and stressful working conditions. Milkovic and Boudreau (1991) further posit that Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) have a broad scope. It covers the: promotion and maintenance of the highest degree of physical, mental and social well-being of workers in occupations; prevention among workers of adverse effects on health caused by their working conditions; protection of workers in their employment from risks resulting from factors adverse to health; placing and maintenance of workers in an occupational environment adapted to physical and mental needs; adaptation of work to humans.

Statement of the problem

Indications are that the provision of health and safety items in the Ghanaian organisations and especially the construction industry continues to fall behind expectations in spite of much effort to improve the situation. The Ghana Health Service (2007) reported that, Ghana's challenge of mainstreaming OHS practices in its national developmental agenda is certainly mitigated by lack of national OHS policy. Clearly there is a problem with OHS practices in Ghana. Laryea et al (2010), Danso et al (2011) argued that indeed in almost all cases, there were pieces of evidence indicating that the provision of health and safety items the Ghanaian organisations especially construction sites has been compromised.

The minister of health Mr Yieleh Chireh said "safety of a workforce was vital to the nation's economic growth. Ghana was saddled with a myriad

of occupational health challenges most of which it had taken for granted either out of ignorance or the blatant refusal to invest in safety. We are all witness to the recent reports of injury following an explosion at Tema Steel Company. This is just the tip of the iceberg as hundreds of incidents occur around the country on a daily basis but do not hit the headlines." (<http://www.citifmonline.com/mobile/index.Php?id=1.454788>).

The above situation is very confusing in the sense that the Labour Act 651 enjoins both employers and employees to ensure that Occupational Health and Safety requirements at the work place are complied with. It is from this background that the study aims to investigate into occupational health and safety practices in Ghanaian organisations.

Objectives of the study

The general objective of the study was to examine the occupational health and safety practices in Ghanaian organisations. The study sought specifically to:

1. To examine employers or leadership responsibilities in the execution of health and safety programmes in the organisations.
2. To assess the level of compliance of occupational health and safety procedures and practices by employees in the organisation.
3. Examine the level of employers and employees awareness of occupational health and safety policies in the organisations
4. Assess organisation's commitment to health and safety practices.
5. To identify effect of health and safety practices on organisation's performances.

Research questions

1. What are employers or leadership level of responsibilities in the execution of health and safety programmes in the organisations?
2. What is the level of compliance of occupational health and safety procedures and practices by employees in the organisation?
3. What is the level of employees' awareness of occupational health and safety policies in the organisations?
4. What is the level of organisation's commitment to health and safety practices?
5. Do health and safety practices affect organisation's performances?

Significance of the study

The study could provide bases for the formulation of effective occupational health and safety policies in the three selected organisations (Ghana Port and Harbours Authority (GHAPPHA), NESTLE, GHACEM). The piece of work will also provide the opportunity for employees, employers to identify their specific respective roles in health and safety issues. It will also provide bases for other organisations in Ghana to adopt the recommendations in the formation of effective health and safety measures in their institutions as well. The work will be used as reference material for policy makers in making decisions concerning health and safety practices and policies and it will contribute to the scanty literature available on this area in Ghana.

Organization of the study

The study is organized into five (5) Chapters. Chapter one gives a general overview of the study. The chapter also talks about the background to

the study and the statement of the problem. It also discusses the research questions, the purpose, significance, limitations and organization of the study.

Chapter Two reviews the available literature with regards to occupational health and safety practices from local and international perspective. The chapter also looks at some models or theories of occupational health and safety practices. Chapter Three deals with the methodology of the study and it spells out the research design used in the study. The Chapter also explains the study area and sampling procedure used in the data collection. The chapter also discusses how the data was collected, processed and analysed for the study.

Chapter Four deals with the presentation and discussion of the findings of the study. Chapter five, the final chapter of this study, provides the summary of and conclusions from what have been discussed in the previous chapters and ends with recommendations that are aimed at addressing the research questions posed earlier in the study.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

Background of the study

Occupational health and safety issues in most of the African countries are due to inadequate attention given to OHS by industry and the government. Many international and non- governmental organisations often ask why majority of the African countries are struggling to foster an effective occupational health and safety workplace. One perspective to the above concern is that majority of African countries have poor health and safety culture (Regional Committee for Africa Report, 2004). Additionally, the reason might be that, greater emphasize is laid on increasing productivity and profitability whiles compromising health and safety standards, procedures and policies. Another OHS perspective for Africa is that, Africa's slowness in promoting occupational health and safety is due to colonialism and its effects on socioeconomic development (Meredith, 1986).

A lot of occupational health and safety risks, accidents, and hazards proliferate in most African countries. According to Amweelo (2000), in his investigation in industrial accidents in Namibia, some occupational health and safety issues such as careless attitudes toward work which leads to risk and hazards of work, and therefore revealed common industrial incidents at the workplace. In South Africa, more than 300, 000 incidents are said to take place every year indicating the proliferation of occupational health and safety risk, hazards and diseases (Bell, 2007).

Occupational health and safety remain neglected in developing countries in Africa because of competing national and sector issues and challenges (Nuwayhid, 2004). To substantiate the above issue, the Regional Committee for Africa Report (2004) stipulated that due to endemic poverty and poor performance of African economies, the African region is faced with a number of OHS challenges. According to this report, Africa's challenge is how to ensure that workers in both the informal sector and formal sector have adequate health and safety education and are able to actively use this information to better their health and safety practices. Probably, ignorance might be the reason for the neglect of occupational health and safety practices and investment in African countries.

In 2000, there was a WHO/ILO joint effort on occupational health and safety in Africa with many collaborators such as USA, EU, WHO, and ICOH for the purpose of sharing information on occupational health and safety; building capacity for occupational health and safety; and formulating policies and legislations for employee health and safety in Africa. In recent time, fairly significant institutional and legal developments (Ladou, 2003) have been identified in few African countries. The above demonstrates the state of OHS in African countries which may be typical in Ghana.

Conceptual framework of the literature review

The literature review is conceptualised to review literature using the objectives of the study as the thematic areas for the review. The aim of the review is gather information on what others have done on the major objective of the study. The literature review will help in testing the reliability of the

study. This is because it will be used to confirm or disproof the findings from the field so that consistencies with other studies can be established.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

In this regard, the review started with looking into the evolution and theoretical underpinnings of the study, this was followed by looking what others have done in the area of occupational health and safety policies and practices. The review further gathered information on inadequacies in occupational health safety in organisations and then the roles and responsibilities of the employers and employees in occupational health and safety. The review at end addresses the issues of compliance and awareness to occupational health and safety issues.

The evolution of OHS theory and regulation and the theoretical underpinning of the study

An early study into safety management in 1931 is the Heinrich’s Domino Theory. In the theory Heinrich identified a chain of events and

circumstances that ultimately lead to injury as: environmental factors, fault of the individual, unsafe act or condition, accident, and injury (Cliff, 2012). Heinrich analysed a large number of industrial accidents and determined that 88 percent were due to unsafe acts, and only 10 percent due to unsafe conditions. The work of Heinrich formed the basis for subsequent OHS management theory. Cliff (2012) argued that as a result a similar finding emerged from the development of the Safety Engineering Model (SEM) shown in Figure 1. The model confirmed a similar balance in terms of unsafe acts 85 percent and unsafe conditions 15 percent. Propounders of the model further suggested that unsafe acts are best prevented through education and enforcement, whereas unsafe conditions are best prevented through improved engineering practices and enforcement of these practices.

Figure 2: Safety Engineering Model (SEM)

The model was further developed to include management and worker behaviour. This aspect focused on the following elements: empowerment of workers, adoption of progressive labour practices, promotion of health and safety as a personal and organisational value, development of positive worker attitudes, with a focus on behaviour modification, and application of ergonomic and human factor analyses. Furthermore, a focus on occupational health in the workplace was added to the framework.

As a result the following elements for protecting and promoting the health of employees in the workplace were introduced: prevention and control of occupational diseases and accidents, development and promotion of a healthy and safe workplace, enhancement of the physical, mental and social wellbeing of employees, and, empowerment of employees to conduct socially and economically productive lives. The above early studies and developments influenced the emergence of a better systematic approach to OHS in the workplace environment.

Theory and approaches to OHS regulation

The need for a global OHS legislation and practice occurred in 1972 when the classical approach of being uniformly prescriptive, with an emphasis on detailed and highly technical specifications and standards, and with compliance to rules enforced by government-funded independent inspectorates with broad inspection powers became challenged with some weakness (Cliff, 2012). Organisational culture has in recent times been introduced into OHS management approaches. According to Cliff (2012), many researchers have investigated the influence of company culture on OHS performance, and

applied the concept of Maturity Models to this area. The maturity model is developed on the basis that improving OHS culture can be characterised in terms of a number of ascending steps (levels) including emerging; managing; involving; co-operation; and continually improving. According to maturity model analytical tools can be applied to assess performance against different management and organisational elements to identify current position on the maturity ladder. Many large resource companies have applied this model to engage all employees in improving OHS performance and culture.

Empirical literature review on occupational health and safety practices/policies

According to Glanville, Schilling, and Wood (1992), the Occupational Health and Safety Act 2000 specifies the minimum requirements for OHS employers are expected to; minimize occupational accidents, diseases and disabilities, promote good health at the work place, promote a good work environment for workers and those in proximity. Employers should carry out their own health and safety risk assessment, in consultation with the occupational health and safety committee, to determine what hazards are present at the workplace. Once the hazards have been identified, controls for exposure to these hazards should be detailed in the health and safety program in order to; to clearly demonstrate management's full commitment to their employee's wellbeing, to show employees that safety performance and business performance are compatible, to clearly state the company's safety beliefs, principles, objectives, strategies and processes through all levels of the company, to clearly outline employer and employee accountability and

responsibility for workplace health and safety, to comply with the Occupational Health and Safety Act, and to set out safe work practices and procedures to be followed to prevent workplace injuries and illnesses (Glanville, Schilling, & Wood, 1992).

The Ghanaian context of occupational health and safety issues

Many key OHS issues proliferate in the Ghanaian economy. The one key OHS issue pertains to dealing with OHS challenges. Obviously, the country has come to OHS late with difficult challenges for OHS practices. One of the major challenges of occupational health and safety practice is that, like many African countries, Ghana cannot boast of any comprehensive national OHS policy. This challenge was observed by Ghana Health Service (2007) which reported that, Ghana's challenge of mainstreaming OHS practices in its national developmental agenda is certainly mitigated by lack of national OHS policy. The issue of policy framework is commonly regarded as African countries most difficult challenge in the sense that policies do not work. Clark (2005) indicated that majority of Ghana's legal provisions on OHS is limited in scope as vast majority of industries, including agriculture and most of the informal sectors are not specifically covered. However, few statutes inform the implementation of occupational health and safety. These are the Factories, Offices and Shops Act 1970, Act328 and the Mining Regulations 1970 LI 665 which have driven OHS implementation in the manufacturing, shipping and mining sectors. Other statutes that have a bearing on OHS are the Workmen's Compensation Law 1987, Environmental Protection Agency Act 490, 1994, and the Ghana Health Service and Teaching

Hospitals Act 526, 1999. But these few legal provisions require huge modification to meet international requirements and standards.

Further, the Ministry of Health Report (2007) also identified some OHS challenges in Ghana. These include weak OHS infrastructures, untrained and inadequate OHS professionals, and lack of proper monitoring and surveillances for occupational health and safety diseases and injuries. In support, Muchiri (2003) buttressed these problem scenarios by indicating that, poor OHS infrastructure and funding, insufficient number of qualified occupational health and safety practitioners and the general lack of adequate information are among the main drawbacks to an effective OHS practices. Kheni (2008) conducted a survey on health and safety practices among construction SMEs and revealed serious OHS problems. The main problems identified by Kheni included lack of skilled human resources, inadequate government support for regulatory institutions and inefficient institutional frameworks responsible for health and safety standards.

The Ghana Labour Act 2003, Act 651 states that an employer shall; provide and maintain at workplace, plant and system of work that are safe and without risk to health, ensure that safety and absence of risks of health in connection with use, handling, storage and transport of articles and substances, provide the necessary information, instructions, training and supervision having regard to the age, literacy level and other circumstances of the worker to ensure, so far as if reasonably practicable, the health and safety at work of those other workers engaged on the particular work, The Act again states that an employer who, without reasonable excuse, fails to discharge any of the

obligations listed above commits an offence and is liable on summary conviction to fine not exceeding 1000 penalty units or to imprisonment for a term not exceeding three years or to both.

The roles and responsibilities of employers and employees in OHS

Occupational health and safety of employees and visitors to workplace is an important issue for both employees and employers Doan (2001)

Leadership or employer's role

In the view of Warmick (2008), leadership is the quality that transforms good intentions into positive action, in turns a group of individuals into a team. The quality and consistency of leadership demonstrated by management influences the attainment of safety management objectives and it is a role model for safety exercise (Ismail, 2007).

Figure 3: Employers' responsibility in Occupational Health and Safety

Source: Clewett (2008)

Through effective leadership, the employer is able to energise the employee to take OSH to the next level. According to Michael, Guo, Wiedenbeck and Ray (2006) positive leadership improved safety behaviour of the employees. GoA (2008) reported that employers have the obligation to ensure that all their employees are protected from health and safety risks arising out of their work activities. This implies employers have to: provide and maintain safe systems of work, make arrangements for ensuring the safe use, handling, storage and transport of equipment or substances, provide necessary information, instruction, training and supervision.

In that case it entails employers to: provide a safe and healthy workplace, establish Occupational Health Committees or representatives and consult and cooperate with them in resolving health and safety concerns, ensure workers are not exposed to harassment, comply with the Occupational Health and Safety Act and Regulations, provide required safe work procedures, ensure equipment is provided and maintained, ensure workers are trained, and ensure supervisors are competent. They are also required to have a copy of the Occupational Health and Safety Act, 1993 and the Occupational Health and Safety Regulations, 1996 readily available to both workers and management. A detail outline of the employers' responsibility in Occupational Health and Safety is provided in Figure 3.

Employee's Role

There must be a complement between roles of employers and that of employees. Employees are specifically supposed to work in a safe manner, be safety conscious on their jobs and co-operate with their employers in the

health and safety measures they put in place. Employees must also work safely to protect themselves and others from injury (GoA, 2008). Employees must for not: move or deface signs, tamper with machine guards, behave in a way that puts others at risk. The OHS Act (2000) indicates that all employees share equal responsibility and so must obey all health and safety procedures, including correctly wearing all personal protective equipment provided and should also know emergency procedures, the location of the first aid kit and report any workplace hazards to employers.

OHS awareness through Training and Development of employees

Additionally, insufficient OHS education has been one of the challenges to occupational health and safety practices (Ministry of Health Report, 2007). Another key OHS issue is the employees' incessant exposure to occupational health and safety hazards, risks and diseases. Liu (1995) reports that small organisations have the highest incidence of work-related injuries and Liu (1993) and Tsai (1995) further argued that these work-related injuries and accidents were significantly associated with insufficient knowledge and unsafe behaviours for both employers and employees. According to Tsai those who did not take occupational health education programmes were fivefold more likely to encounter occupational injuries than those who took programmes. Lee et al. (1991) posited that workers learned knowledge and skills regarding occupational health and safety (OHS) informally from co-workers and employers. On this basis, Lee et al. (1991) further argued that employers' comprehension of occupational health was not only an important source of employees' knowledge and behaviour related to workplace health

and safety but also a significant determinant of the level of good safety and health of the workplace.

Ian et al. (2003) discovered from their survey a very low level of awareness of relevant health and safety legislation, with 63 percent of respondents unable to identify any health and safety legislation affecting their business. According to them awareness of health and safety legislation was significantly higher among larger enterprises in the sample than in smaller businesses. They cited that 35 percent of businesses with less than five staff referred to at least one piece of health and safety legislation compared with 42 percent of businesses with five or more). Awareness level was also higher in the construction industry (53%), which is a higher risk activity, than in the other sectors, where between 31 percent and 38 percent of respondents did so. Though the small organisations had less than five (5) employees and have limited exemption from some legislative requirements (e.g. written health and safety policy and a written record of health and safety risk assessment), the level of awareness is very low.

In regards to compliance Ian et al. (2003) discovered that less than 10 percent of the surveyed enterprises reported difficulties in complying with health and safety legislation, although this partly reflects the low level of awareness . Although businesses experiencing inspection visits were more likely to complain that health and safety regulations were too burdensome for various reasons, the survey and other findings suggest that, on the whole, inspectors are adopting a predominantly persuasive and educative approach, using enforcement actions, particularly prosecution, as a last resort.

Safety behaviour and safety compliance practices

Mahmood (2010) explains that safety behaviour refers to the behaviour that support safety practices and activities such as providing safety training and safety compliance explains the core activities that need to be carried by employees according to occupational, safety and health requirements to prevent workplace accidents. Safety behaviour is the key reducing the injuries at the workplace and indirectly influencing the outcomes of the event before the injuries or accidents occurred (Johnson, 2003).

Safety compliance is ranged from good to poor where comply with safety requirements remark as good safety compliance and not comply with safety requirements remark as poor safety compliance. Fredericks' (1982) ABC model of behaviour as cited in Abang et al. (2005) as shown on Table 4, explained that behaviour is influenced by two distinct factors: activators and consequences. Thus the enforcement on safety behaviour factors plays the crucial role to encourage safety compliance before the consequences occurred.

Figure 4: Change behaviour interventions
Source: Abang et al. (2005)

Safety Compliance vs. Non-compliance with Safety Requirements

Noncompliance to safety requirements is by far the major contributory factor in incident and accident occurrence. Compliance with safety requirements will help that the work can be done both efficiently and safely. Che et al. (2007) explained that one very promising line of enquiry concerning the behavioural antecedents of accidents concerns the relationship among these procedural instructions governing work and the way in which work is done .That is to say much could be improved with enough room for improvement towards behavioural safety compliance through strong effort to comply with safety requirements by both employers and employees.

The behavioural safety compliance factors

There are several factors of employers' behaviour that contributes to encourage employees' safety compliance to occupational, safety and health improvement policies in the workplace. In their pilot study to the industry using interview questionnaires survey, Zin and Ismail (2012) identified ten major factors - management commitment, organisational commitment, safety communication, safety leadership, effective safety training, safety motivation, safety management system, safety guidelines and regulation, safety and health officer, personal protective equipment (PPE) - that can give positive impetus towards improving safety compliance in the construction industry.

Management commitment to health and safety practices in organisation

It is a crucial responsibility of top management to lead the organization and employees towards achievement of organization safety goals by showing that the organization is serious about safety. In this regard Jaselski et al.

(1996) reported that commitment and support by top management would significantly drive up the performance of safety and Fernando et al. (2008) further argued that the employer should demonstrate commitment through strongly realization of safety compliance to safety requirements and ensure that everyone in the organization is certain about their safety and health responsibilities.

The researchers identified manager commitment factors of realisation of safety compliance in Petrochemical Processing Area as; properly constituted joint safety and health committees at site and departmental level, accountability of managers to the joint safety and health committee, engagement of safety and health representatives with the health and safety practitioners, dialogue among local area and line managers within the establishment of safety and health representatives, the provision time of facility to have the safety and health representative functions such as joint safety and health inspection, investigations of employees complaint, making representations to managers to managers and so on, involvement of safety and health representatives in reporting and monitoring on OSH, access of safety and health representatives to employees and access to have training for safety and health representatives. Thus Thye (2006) argued that management commitment towards safety and health at the workplace can change behaviour of their employees.

Organisational commitment to health and safety practices

The extent to which an employee identifies with and involved in an organisation is referred to as organisational commitment (Curry, Wakefield,

Price & Mueller, 1986). Bakshi et al. (2009) discovered that organisation commitment is a critical factor in understanding and explaining the work related behaviour of employees in organizations and their study Hofmann and Mergeson (1999) found organization support and commitment on employee safety and quality of exchange relationships between supervisors and subordinates safety behaviour and reduced accidents.

Safety Communication

Non-compliance to safety requirements are normally the cause of work base related accidents. Effective communications is important to safe and efficient workplace environment. According to Ismail (2007), leaders convey vision and values through interaction and communication and that effective communication leads to commonly understood goals and mean to achieve them at all level. Zohar (2002) discovered improved communication channel resulted to a decrease in micro accidents and increased in using Personal Protective Equipment (PPE). Thus effective communication can be achieved in three ways. The first is through visible behaviour, employer can communicates the importance of safety and health. Employees soon recognize what employer regard as important and will adopt their own behaviour accordingly. Thus, through negative behaviour employer can undermines the safety and health culture of the organization. The second is written communication of Health and safety policy statements, statements concerning health and safety roles and responsibilities, performance standards and findings from risk assessments and the third is face to face discussions between employer and employee. This enables employees to make a personal

contribution and helps employees feel involved in the safety and health of the organization.

OHS awareness through effective safety training and development

Ghani et al. (2010) posited that effective safety training is important to educate employees on potential of accidents, how to prevent accidents and potential hazards involved in their jobs. The training and education programs play a significant role in enhancement of safety and important to increase safety awareness. Wong et al. (2000) further added that training changes the behaviour of employees. McDonald (2003) established in his study that of 18 construction site in Ireland that safety training is carried out without systematic schedule which primarily to “cover themselves” and protect company if something goes wrong with little expectation that it would influence the knowledge and behaviour of employees. This means that majority of employees have to gain knowledge of risks of their work through their experience of work itself. O’Toole (2002) discovered that insufficient safety training between the employees are the general root cause of accidents in the construction sites because they did not have the knowledge, education and skills to recognize potential hazards at site. Komaki, Heinzman, and Wyld (1980) established from their study that safety training have strong linkage to employees’ safety behaviour improvement.) In addition it is argued that trainings aimed at workers and operator would not only reduce accidents, but may also reduce costs and save lives (Hopton, 1969).

HSE and organisational performance

Senior level management relating with employees in terms of talking and advising them on safety matters helps to improve safety motivation and will encourage safety behaviour among employees (Che et al., 2007). Evelyn (2005) argued that a positive reinforcement type of motivation gives employees outcomes such as monetary rewards, bonuses and job promotion but a negative reinforcement type of motivation employers criticize, punish and threaten the employees to motivate them to safely perform their jobs. However, reinforcement on positive motivation is more encourage by many safety practitioner to maintain improve employees' good safety behaviour. There will only be improvement in safety if incentives schemes are carried out to motivate employees to change their behaviours (Vrenderburgh, 2002). Thus Leung et al. (2004) explained that the organization that creates and maintain good quality employer and employee relationships benefits from higher levels of the employee motivation, commitment and job satisfaction, which consequently leads to low labour turn over and influences employee performance.

Safety Management System and OHS policies

It is the responsibility of management to put in place and implement a sound OSH management system that involves proper risk assessments, reporting systems, safety plan, clear delegation of responsibilities, provide adequate resources and ensure that full information is disseminated to workers and other person exposed to risks (Muhammad, 2006). As part of management having an effective safety management system there must be the

documentation of risk assessment and they have to meet legislative requirements relevant to their specific work environment. In many overseas constructions site, some or all the management level had undertaken CIF/CEF training courses which seem to gain better safety compliance. It is recommended for management level to undertake special training course especially on behavioural aspect which perceived to give them basis on managing uncertainty of human behaviour and training course in safety and health management system to ensure it can be effectively deliver to supervise employees towards behavioural safety compliance.

Safety procedures guidelines and regulation

Adherence to safety guidelines and regulations promotes compliance and occupational health and safety practices at the work place. The main document that gives a legislative framework to promote and encourage high standards of safety and health at work is the occupational, safety and health act (OSHA) of 1994 (Ismail, 2010). However, according to Jamal (2003), employee's poor perception on employer compliance to safety requirements could lead to negative behaviour and correlate with poor safety performance which carries enormous negative consequences to the individual and the organisation where they work.

Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

It is the employer's responsibility to ensure that employees wear safety tools to keep their safety. The employer must provide protective personal equipment to the workers, especially for those that work in construction sites to reduce the death of the worker if they wear personal protective equipment

(Harris & McCaffer, 1982). Duff et al. (1993) found percentages of non-compliance with specific categories in six construction sites ranging from 22-38 percent of noncompliance in housekeeping, from 12-43 percent of noncompliance in scaffolding, from 20-26 percent of noncompliance in access-to-heights, and from 21-65 percent of non-compliance in using PPE. Furthermore it was discovered that in the United Kingdom that non-compliance was around 19 percent for housekeeping, 16 percent for scaffolding, 15 percent for access to height and 21 percent for PPE (Robertson et al., 1999). In another study in Hong Kong percentage ranging from 30-49 percent for housekeeping, from 30-66 percent for bamboo scaffolding, from 50-74 percent for access to heights and 49-69 percent of non-compliance for PPE was reported (Lingard et al., 1997).

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

Introduction

This Chapter discusses the methodology followed for the study. It includes the description of the study area, study design, target population, sampling frame, sample size as well as sampling technique. The sources of data, data collection and research instruments were also explained in detail.

Description of study area

Tema, which serves as the administrative capital of the Tema Metropolitan is a coastal city situated 25 kilometres east of Accra, the national capital. The Greenwich Meridian (00 Longitude) passes through the city of Tema (http://www.ghanadistricts.com/districts/?news&r=1&_=4). It was created in 1951 as a well-planned township and an industrial city. The metropolitan area shares boundaries northwards and eastwards with the Dangme West District Assembly (DWDA), on the west with the Accra Metropolitan Assembly (AMA) and on the north-west with the Ga District Assembly (GDA). On the south it is bounded by the Gulf of Guinea. The Greenwich Meridian '0' degree Longitude passes through the city of Tema. Over 80% of the population of the Municipality is concentrated in the major settlements in the municipality: Tema (capital), Ashaiman and Tema Manhean. The township is the pivot around which the entire municipality revolves. It has well planned industrial and commercial areas, which constitute the economic hallmark of the nation (Tema Municipality Human Development

Report, 2004). The Municipality hosts the industrial nerve centre of the country and therefore attract of a large number of migrants.

Figure 5: The map of Tema Municipality

Source: www.i.nona.net

The population of the Municipality stood at 506,400 in 2000 when the census was conducted. Less than 10% of the population lives in rural communities. More than half of the economically active population is employed in the services sector. Unemployment rate in the Municipality was estimated at 11.7% in 2003. This is higher than the national unemployment rate of 5.5% (Tema Municipality Human Development Report, 2004).

The Tema port covers an area of 3.9 million square metres. It is located close to the Tema the industrial city and it happens to be the biggest sea port in Ghana. Over 1650 vessels call on the port in a year. The port provides logistic services for warehouse, inland Clearance Depots (ICDs), transport and haulage companies, freight forwarders etc. (ghanaports.gov.gh/tm/default).

Nestlé Ghana Limited commenced operations under the trade name of Nestlé Products (Gh) Limited. At its start-up in Ghana it went into the importation of milk and chocolates from Nestlé. However, in 1968, the company became known as Food Specialties (Gh) Limited. Its objective was to manufacture and market locally well-known Nestlé brands. Consequently the company became known as Nestlé Ghana Limited in 1987. Nestlé started local production of Ideal Milk and milo in 1971 at its factory in Tema. The factory now produces carnation milk, Choclim, Chocomilo, Cerevita, Cerelac, and NESCAFÉ for the local and international market (http://www.ghanayello.com/company/36021/Nestle_Ghana_Limited). On the other hand, GHACEM was founded by the Government of Ghana in collaboration with Norcem AS of Norway, on August 30, 1967. It has since then produced more than 30 million tons of cement (<http://www.heidelbergcement.com/africa/en/ghacem/home.htm>).

Study design

The research is a descriptive research. It made use of both qualitative and quantitative tools in analysing the data gathered through structured interview schedule. Kumar (2005) argued that any study that aims at finding out the prevalence of a phenomenon at the time of the study is known as a cross-sectional study. The study falls in the category of descriptive,

exploratory as well as explanatory research, which is described mostly as applied studies. To answer the main research questions in this study, the study employed the 'cross-sectional study design type'. This design allows for views to be gathered from a selected sample of the population being investigated, with an appropriate sampling technique to effectively reflect the views of the population being studied (Kumar, 2005). In this regard three companies - Ghana Port and Harbours Authority (GHAPPOHA), NESTLE, and GHACEM were selected from the Tema Municipality respectively for the study.

Target population

The population targeted for the collection of data for the study comprise of all employees of Ghana Port and Harbours Authority, NESTEL and GHACEM who face the danger of suffering from occupational hazards at work.

Sample and sampling procedures

Before selecting the study sample, the researcher first identified the population that formed the sources of data (Marshalls & Rossman 1995; Keith, 1998) in line with the methodology demanded for designing qualitative research. The study sample was drawn from three companies in Tema, namely Ghana Port and Harbours Authority, NESTLE, and GHACEM. The researcher got the sampling frame from each of the companies as shown in Table 1 then both stratified and simple random sampling techniques were adopted to select a sample size of one hundred and fifty employees. With regards to stratified sampling technique, the researcher segmented each of the company's staff

from the various departments and units into four strata comprising of twenty elements out of which ten was sampled. Namely the strata are senior management (SM), middle level management (MM), lower level management (LM) - Supervisors/Forman and the subordinates (S).

Table 1: Sampled Sampling Companies and Procedure

Company	Sampling Frame	Strata				Number Sampled
		SM	MM	LM	S	
Ghana Port and Harbours Authority	1000	20	20	20	40	50
NESTLE,	800	20	20	20	40	50
GHACEM	600	20	20	20	40	50
Total	2400	60	60	60	120	150

Source: Field survey, 2014

In order to give each element in each strata equal opportunity of been selected into the sample, the simple random sampling technique was used to select ten elements from the senior level management, middle level management, lower level management strata respectively and twenty elements from the subordinate strata of company as shown in Table 1. The number of elements from the subordinate strata is more because they are more prone to organisational hazards

Data sources

The study used both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected through structured interviews with the respondents, observation of the physical working environment. A total of 150 structured interview/questionnaire were used to collect data. The duration of the interviews ranged between 10-45 minutes each. The secondary data were gathered from official statistics and other information on occupational health safety obtained from the offices of the sampled organizations, previous researches, books, journal articles and web information. In order to get a better understanding and increased knowledge about occupational health and safety policies, practices as well as expanding knowledge about the situation of occupational health and safety in Ghana, a review of the above documents was done. This helped to retrieve valuable data concerning the situation of the disabled. The researcher undertook personal observation through the companies work environment to examine the design, provision of exit entrances, waste disposal systems among others. The researcher again visited the departments and units of the selected companies to understand their system of operation and to be sure that staff comply with safety measures in the discharge of their duties.

Research instruments and data collection

The main instruments used to collect data were structures questionnaires/interview schedules. These were administered to the one hundred and fifty sampled respondents from the three companies. The questionnaire contained both closed and open-ended questions. The open-ended questions gave the opportunity to explore issues concerning respective

items on the questionnaire while the close-ended questions were also used to restrict the respondents to some specific items of interest to the study. Data collection ended at the close of April, 2014 and secondary data collection for the study in mid-May, 2014. This afforded the researcher to blend theoretical findings with empirical verifications from the field. However, at the end of the period one hundred and thirty-six questionnaires were correctly and fully completed and were summarised and used for results presentation and discussion.

Pre-test

A pre-test was conducted at the Tema Metropolis. It was used to test the data processing and analysis procedures. GHACEM was used for the pre-test. Five respondents were interviewed and their responses analysed. Each interview lasted for about forty-five minutes. GHACEM was selected because it is situated in Tema Metropolis, the study area.

Analytical Techniques

Data analysis was done by the use of a combination of thematic discussion of qualitative information and the use of percentages, ratios, tables, charts, graphs and cross-tabulations. Microsoft Excel 2010 was used to organise the data for the study and the information presented in the above mentioned forms and their discussion followed.

Challenges of the study

The main challenge was paucity of funds. This made it difficult covering the wide study area. To overcome this challenge the researcher had to borrow money from friends and relatives to be able to reach the scattered

organisations in the study area. There was also apathy and lack of cooperation on the part of some of the respondents. They argued that a few of such interviews they granted yielded no results in their conditions. This challenge was overcome through education, persuasion and giving them financial tips. However, three respondents refused to be interviewed hence a haphazard sampling approach was used to select and interview three more respondents.

CHAPTER FOUR
RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Introduction

This chapter presents results and discussions using one hundred and thirty-six structured interview/ questionnaires which were fully answered by respective respondents (employees) from GHACEM, NESTLE and GHAPOHA in the Tema Municipality (TMA) on health and safety related issues.

Analysis respondents' demographic attributes

Demographic discussion in this research include respondents' gender, age, and education

Respondents' gender distribution

Table 2 shows respondents' gender distribution. From Table 2, 32% of the respondents are female whiles the remaining 67.65% of the respondents are male. This gender distribution showed that more male participated in the survey and may imply that there are more male in the manufacturing industry of Ghana.

Table 2: Respondents' gender distribution

Gender	Frequency	Percentage, %
Female	44	32.35
Male	92	67.65
Total	136	100.00

Author's field work, 2014

Respondents' age distribution

Respondents' ages were also captured for analysis and discussion as shown on Table 2. From Table 2, 16.18% of the respondents were between the ages of 18 and 27 years while 19.12% of the respondents were between the ages of 26 and 33 years. However, majority (34.56%) of the respondents were between the ages of 34 to 41 years old. Respondents' age distribution showed that about 69.85% of the respondents are between 18 and 41 years. This implies most of the respondents are within the active working ages.

Table 3: Respondents' age distribution

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage, %
18-25	22	16.18
26-33	26	19.12
34-41	47	34.56
42-49	36	26.47
50-57	5	3.68
58-65	0	0.00
66-73	0	0.00
Total	136	100.00

Author's field work, 2014

Respondents' educational level

For employees to understand basic health and safety standards, they need some basic education. This would help them to read health and safety manuals and implement them. From Table 4, it was observed that majority (30.15%) of the respondents have secondary school education as their highest educational level while only 5.88% of the respondents have advanced degree

educational level. However, 25% of the respondents hold first degree qualification as their highest educational level compared with 28% of the respondents have diploma certificate as their highest qualification. This educational distribution of respondents showed that about 50.74% of the respondents have either secondary or diploma qualification as their highest qualification. This implies that employees in the manufacturing sector have basic qualification necessary to read and understand health and safety procedures in their respective workplaces

Table 4: Respondents' educational level

Education	Frequency	Percentage, %
Secondary	41	30.15
Diploma	28	20.59
First Degree	34	25.00
Advanced Degree	8	5.88
Professional Qualification	25	18.38
Total	136	100.00

Author's field work, 2014

Analysis of Respondents career background

Respondents' company

This research collected data from three manufacturing companies, namely GHAPOHA, NESTLE, GHACEM all from Tema of the Greater Region of Ghana. Table 5, shows that 30.88 of the respondents are from NESTLE whiles 33.09% of the respondents are from GHAPOHA. The remaining 36.03% of the respondents are from GHACEM.

Table 5: Respondents' company

Company	Frequency	Percentage, %
GHAPOHA	42	30.88
NESTLE	45	33.09
GHACEM	49	36.03
Total	136	100.00

Author's field work, 2014**Respondents' job category**

From Table 6, majority (68.38%) of the respondents are production floor workers or operatives whiles 6.625 of the respondents are administrative officers. However, 12.5% of the respondents are team managers compared with 3.68% of the respondents who are controllers.

Table 6: Respondents' job category

Job Category	Frequency	Percentage, %
Controller	5	3.68
Line Manager	12	8.82
Team Manager	17	12.50
Administrative Officer	9	6.62
Operative/Floor Staff	93	68.38
Total	136	100.00

Author's field work, 2014

Respondents' work experience

Level of experiences play important role in the level of following safety rules in organisations. From Table 7, it was observed that 20.59% of the respondents have less than a year experience in their respective company while 49.26% of the respondents have between one year and 4 years of work experience with their company. However, 30.155 of the respondents have more than four years of work experience in their company. This results implies that majority of the respondents have more than one year experience with their companies and therefore should have enough information with the health and safety issues in their respective companies.

Table 7: Respondents' work experience

Work Experience	Frequency	Percentage, %
Less than 1 year	28	20.59
Between 1 and 4 years	67	49.26
More than 4 years	41	30.15
Total	136	100.00

Author's field work, 2014

Analysis of health and safety as part of organisation's leadership issues

Health and safety must be an important part of organisation's leadership (Clewett, 2008). From Table 8, respondents were asked to provide their views on how health and safety issues are part of their organisation's leadership. The results showed that majority (49.26%) of the respondents strongly agreed that leadership view organisations health and safety as shared

responsibility and not only the responsibilities of the floor workers or subordinates while 42.65% of the respondents agreed that leadership view organisations health and safety as shared responsibility and not only the responsibilities of the floor workers or subordinates. This results suggest that only 5.88% of the respondents either disagreed or strongly disagreed that leadership view organisations health and safety as shared responsibility and not only the responsibilities of the floor workers or subordinates while the remaining 2.21% of the respondents did not make any comment to the issue.

Table 8 also showed 42.65% of the respondents strongly agreed that leadership of their company provide excellent health and safety policies while 36.76% of the respondents agreed that excellent health and safety policies are provided by leader of their organisation. On the issue of documentation of health and safety issues in the organisations, majority (40.44%) of the respondents agreed that leadership provide well documented health and safety policies while 37.5% of the respondents strongly agreed to that leadership provide well documented health and safety policies. Again, majority showed that health and safety is a strategic direction of their organisation. In all, leadership steps on health and safety in organisation is consistent with Doan (2001) who explained that health and safety in organisation must be an integral part of an employer's or leadership duty towards engaging in risk management processes in the workplace.

Table 8: Health and safety as part of organisation's leadership

Health and safety and leadership	Likert-Scale				
	Strong disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Leadership views organization's health and safety issues as share responsibility and not only the responsibilities of their subordinates or employees.	1.47	4.41	2.21	42.65	49.26
Leadership provides excellent health and safety policies.	7.35	8.82	4.41	36.76	42.65
Health and safety policies in my organization are well documented and are enforced.	8.82	10.29	2.94	40.44	37.50
Management view health and safety issues as part of organization's	5.15	6.62	5.15	38.97	44.12

operations strategic

direction.

Author's field work, 2014

Analysis of organisation's safety procedures

Table 9 shows respondents' view on health and safety procedures in their organisation. From Table 9 that 26.47% of the respondents strongly agreed that employees always follow safety work procedures while 30.88% of the respondents agreed that employees follow safety procedures in their organisations. However, 22.79% of the respondents disagreed that employees followed health and safety procedures while 18.38% of the respondents strongly disagreed to the statement that employees follow health and safety procedures. In all, majority (57.35%) of the respondents agreed that employees followed safety procedures in their workplace. Table 9 also shows that 27.21% and 24.26% of the respondents strongly disagreed or agreed respectively that employees always report safety accidents compared with 20.59% and 22.06% of the respondents who agreed or strongly disagreed respectively that employees always report safety accidents. This results show that 51.47% (majority) of the respondents generally disagreed that employees always report safety accidents. This suggests most employees do not report safety accidents. This practice of not always reporting safety accidents is not consistent with OHS Act (2000) which also requires that employees must report any workplace hazards to employers.

Table 9 also shows that majority (30.15%) of the respondents strongly agreed that safety procedures are updated regularly while 27.21% of the

respondents agreed that safety procedures are updated regularly. On the issue of employee involvement on the review of safety procedures, 26.47% and 28.68% of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively that employees are regularly involved in reviewing safety procedures. This shows that generally, management do not regularly involved employees in reviewing health and safety issues. This management practices observed is not consistent with Downey et al. (1995) who explained that employees' basic rights includes the rights to know about workplace safety hazards and the right to participate in the occupational health and safety process. Employee's poor perception on employer compliance to safety requirements could lead to negative behaviour and correlate with poor safety performance which carries enormous negative consequences to the individual and the organisation where they work (Jamal, 2003).

Table 9: Organisation's safety procedures

Organization's safety procedures		Likert-Scale				
		Strong disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Employees	always follow safe work procedures in my organization.	18.38	22.79	1.47	30.88	26.47
Employees	always report safety incidents	27.21	24.26	5.88	20.59	22.06

Table 9 continued

Our company updates	21.32	18.38	2.94	27.21	30.15
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our safe work procedures regularly.

In my organization,	26.47	28.68	5.15	16.18	23.53
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employees are always involved in reviewing safe work procedures.

In my organization,	29.41	20.59	2.21	19.12	28.68
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safety procedures are review regularly.

Author's field work, 2014**Respondents' specific areas or operations with safety concern**

Respondents were asked opened questions on specific areas or operations where accident generally occurred as shown on Table 10. This result showed that 41.18% of the respondents said crane and forklift operation experienced the highest accidents in the organisations, followed by cutting machines with 30.15% respondents. This result implied that safety procedures and other safety measures in the crane/forklift and cutting machines operations are not well enforced to reduce accidents.

Table 10: Respondents' safety concern areas during operations

Safety concern operations or areas	frequency	Percentage, %
Crane/Forklift operations	56	41.18
Cutting machines	41	30.15
Warehouse	22	16.18
Others	17	12.50
Total	136	100.00

Author's field work, 2014

Training and development and health & safety issue

Health and safety training and development are important to organisation's performance. In this research, respondents were asked issues on health and safety training in their organisations as shown in Table 11. From Table 11, it was observed that 51.47% of the respondents strongly agreed that all employees are given health and safety training before they start work while 40.44% of the respondents agreed to that statement. Again majority agreed or strongly agreed that their organisation provide excellent training content which meet their work requirement. On the other hand majority either strongly disagreed or disagreed to the statement that organisation request for feedback after safety training re given to employees. This showed that even though management provides the necessary training on health and safety to employees to ensure that safety risk are clearly defined. This regular training observed is consistent with Komaki et al (1980) and Tsai (1995) who observed that health and safety in organisation is significant to employees' level of understanding and following healthy due process. Tsai (1995) found that

employees who do not take occupational health education programmes were fivefold more likely to encounter occupational injuries than those who took programmes.

Table 11: Training and development as part of health and safety issues

HSE and training and development	Likert-Scale				
	Strong disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
All new employees are given induction training before they start work.	1.47	6.62	0.00	40.44	51.47
My organization has excellent training content which meet health and safety needs of the company.	11.76	13.24	8.82	30.88	35.29
Upon completion of safety training, employees are asked to provide feedbacks.	27.21	28.68	8.82	16.18	19.12
Our safety training is reviewed or updated if there is an incident.	8.82	11.03	6.62	34.56	38.97
All employees get trained in safe work procedures for our jobs.	8.82	10.29	1.47	37.50	41.91

Author's field work, 2014

Analysis of organisation’s commitment to health and safety issues

Organisation’s commitment to health and safety development is important to overall performance. From Table 12, it was observed that 98.53% of the respondents strongly agreed that their organisations provide protective clothing and equipment (PPE). Also all the respondents strongly agreed that in their organisation there is “no PPE no work” policy. Table 12 also shows that 48.53% and 38.97% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively that front line managers and supervisor make sure that works are done in a safely manner at all times. Table 12 also showed that 37.50% of the respondents strongly agreed that management solved all safety issues once they are reported whiles 32.35% of the respondents agreed that management solved all safety issues once they are reported.

Table 12: Organisation’s commitment to health and safety

HSE and training and development	Likert-Scale				
	Strong disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
My organization always provides personal protective clothing and equipment (PPE) to employees before the start work.	0.00	0.00	1.47	0.00	98.53
My organization has “no PPE no work”	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00

policy and are strictly enforced.

Front Line managers	5.88	3.68	2.94	38.97	48.53
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and supervisor make sure that works are done in a safely manner at all times.

Management always	12.50	9.56	8.09	32.35	37.50
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solves any health and safety problems that are reported.

Author's field work, 2014

The results observed from Table 12 suggest that majority of the respondents perceived that there is management commitment to health and safety and this is consistent with Jaselski et al. (1996) who concluded that commitment and support by top management significantly drive up the performance of safety. Bakshi et al. (2009) also observed similar situation and explained that organisation commitment is a critical factor in understanding and explaining the work related behaviour of employees in organizations

Health and safety and organisation's performance

Health and safety issues are significant to high performances in organisations. From Table 13, it was observed that 38.24% of the respondents strongly disagreed that organisation is experiencing high absenteeism due to health and safety issue whiles 30.15% of the respondents agreed to that

statement. On the issue of breaks or interruption in operations, 36.03% of the respondents strongly disagreed to the issue that organisation experience high breaking due to health and safety whiles 29.41% of the disagree to the statement. However, minority (30.15%) of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that organisation experienced high breaks in operations due to health and safety.

Table 13: Health and safety and organisation's performance

HSE and training and development	Likert-Scale				
	Strong disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
My organization is experiencing high absenteeism due to health and safety situation.	38.24	30.15	11.76	8.09	11.76
My organization experience high breaks in operations due to frequent accidents at the workplace.	36.03	29.41	4.41	13.97	16.18
Health and safety management system is part of the core drivers of my organization's performance	6.62	4.41	1.47	40.44	47.06

Author's field work, 2014

Also majority (47.06%) of the respondents strongly agreed health and safety issues are significant drivers of organisations' performance while 40.44% of the respondents agreed to the statement that health and safety issues are significant drivers of organisations' performance. This result generally suggests that health and safety is not causing employees' absenteeism, and interruption in operations. Therefore the result suggests that safety practices are high in these organisations and hence a significant driver to good work environment, job place satisfaction and higher performance in organisations.

This result in Table 13 is consistent with Leung et al. (2004) who observed that organization commits to good work environment, safety practices and relationship, benefits from high employee commitment, job satisfaction and low absenteeism or low employees' turnover and hence high performance.

Employee's opinions to improve health and safety in their organisation

Opened questions asked respondents areas organisations should focus to improve health and safety in their organisation as shown on Table 14.

Table 14: Respondents' views on health and safety improvement

Opinions to improve safety in organization	Frequency	Percentage, %
Monitor employees work procedures	38	27.94
Reduce work overload	57	41.91
Reduce excessive work pressure	23	16.91
Table 14 continued		
Strict record of employee activities	18	13.24
Total	136	100.00

Author's field work, 2014

From Table 14, it was observed that respondents majority (41.91%) of the respondents expressed that organisation should reduce work overload in order to improve safety issues while 27.94% of the respondents expect said organisation should monitor work procedures at workplace to improve safety. Jamal (2003) also observed that employee's poor perception on employer compliance to safety requirements could lead to negative behaviour and correlate with poor safety performance which carries enormous negative consequences to the individual and the organisation where they work.

CHAPTER FIVE
SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND
RECOMMENDATIONS

Introduction

This chapter provides summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations based on the objectives of the study.

Summary of findings

Most countries and industries scarcely recognize occupational health and safety practices as a crucial determinant of national development, especially in the developing countries. Therefore, this paper focused on assessing health and safety practices in the Ghanaian manufacturing industry. Glanville, Schilling, and Wood (1992) explained that the Occupational Health and Safety Act 2000 specifies the minimum requirements for OHS employers are expected to; minimize occupational accidents, diseases and disabilities, promote good health at the work place, promote leadership and management commitment, good work environment for workers and those in proximity. Both stratified and random sampling used to collect data from respondents. The researcher used descriptive and exploratory design and the results presented for discussion and analysis based on the objectives of the study:

Leadership share responsibility

The results showed that majority (40.44%) of the respondents agreed that organisations' leadership provide well documented health and safety policies whiles 37.5% of the respondents strongly agreed to that leadership

provide well documented health and safety policies. Again, majority showed that health and safety is a strategic direction of their organisation. This result suggests that leadership consider health and safety issues as an integral part of an employees' well-being and organisation's performance.

Safety procedures

Results showed that majority (57.35%) of the respondents generally agreed that employees followed safety procedures in their workplace. Also 26.47% of the respondents strongly disagreed that employees are regularly involved in reviewing safety procedures whiles and 28.68% of the respondents disagreed to the statement. This result suggests that majority most employees are not involved in reviewing health and safety issues in their organisations. Again, result showed that 51.47% of the respondents generally disagreed that employees always report safety accidents. This implies that most employees do not always report safety accidents.

Training and development issues

The result showed that majority agreed or strongly agreed that their organisation provide excellent training content which meet their work requirement. On the other hand, majority either strongly disagreed or disagreed to the statement that organisation request for feedback after safety training re given to employees. This implies that though these organisations do provide excellent training and training materials, they do not always call for feedback on the impact of training undertaken on employees.

Organisation's commitment

Results on organisations' commitment to health and safety issues showed that 98.53% of the respondents strongly agreed that their organisations provide protective clothing and equipment (PPE). Also all the respondents strongly agreed that in their organisation there is "no PPE no work" policy. Again, 48.53% the respondents strongly either agreed that front line managers and supervisor make sure that works are done in a safely manner at all times whiles and 38.97% of the respondents strongly agreed to that statement. Also 37.50% of the respondents strongly agreed that management solved all safety issues once they are reported whiles 32.35% of the respondents agreed that management solved all safety issues once they are reported. These results implies that there is high organisation's commitment to health and safety standards in terms of solving safety issues once reported, providing PPE to all employees and ensuring that wearing or using these PPEs are mandatory during working hours.

Health and safety and organisations' performance

Results on the impact of health and safety on organisation's performance showed that most (47.06%) of the respondents strongly agreed health and safety issues are significant drivers of organisations' performance whiles 40.44% of the respondents agreed to the statement that health and safety issues are significant drivers of organisations' performance. This result also suggests that employees' absenteeism, operation interruptions are not due to health and safety issues in the organisation. Also organisation considers health and safety issues as significant driver of organisation's performance.

Conclusions

Health and safety issues in organisations are important to the well-being of employees and performances. This research revealed that management or leadership in these organisations (NESTLE, GHAPOHA and GHACEM) have share responsibility and are committed to health and safety issues in their respective organisations. Also, employees are provided with the necessary training that fit the demand of their skills or task and are provided with the necessary PPEs to ensure that safety operations. However, the result revealed that whiles not all employees followed health and safety procedures in their organisations, most employees also do not always report safety accident issues to management. Also management do not always involved employees in reviewing safety issues and also do no always request for feedback after health and safety training for employees.

Therefore it is important for organisations in Ghana and in particular this three manufacturing companies to know that employees' involvement in reviewing safety issues would promote employees commitment. Also it is a basic right for employees to report any workplace hazard to employers or leadership of the organisation to ensure continuous improvement in their organisation's performances.

Also further research should focused on the health and safety practices of many organisation is the Tema Municipality (TMA) and other regions in Ghana to provide a wider evaluation of the health and safety issues in the country.

Recommendations

This study has revealed some shortcomings in organisations in terms of health and safety issues. Therefore, the following recommendations are necessary:

1. It was revealed that management do not always request for feedback after safety training. Feedbacks ensure that trainers and supervisors know the impact of the training on employees and performance of the organisation. Therefore, it is important that management ensure that feedback from employees become an important part of their control and monitoring system.
2. Health and safety procedures are important to the wellbeing of employees and following standards. Some employees do not follow safety procedure and therefore it is important that safety procedures are repeatedly monitored and controlled to ensure that all employees follow due process in organisation's safety. This implies that organisations should improve safety checks to avoid future accidents.
3. Management should also improve employees' participation during health and safety reviews. This would ensure that employees become part of the organisation's decision making which would motivate them to commit to health and safety issues in the organisations.

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APPENDICES

Questionnaires

CENTRAL UNIVERSITY COLLEGE
BACHELOR OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION

Survey questionnaire

RESEARCH TOPIC: OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND SAFETY
PRACTICES IN GHANAIAN ORGANISATIONS. THE CASE STUDY OF
THREE ORGANISATIONS IN THE TEMA MUNICIPALITY

This survey is part of academic requirement and therefore for only academic purpose and not for any third part use. The researcher intends to understand and assess the health and safety practices in organization in the Tema Metropolis. All employees are voluntarily welcome to participate in this survey. All opinions or views from respondents' shall be highly observed and their right of confidentiality are applied to avoid any situation that may be considered as employee's conflict of interest.

SECTION A: DEMOCGRAPHIC ATTIRBUTES

Instruction:

Please tick "√" your answer.

1. Please indicate your gender

Male Female

2. Where do you work?

Nestle CHACEM GHAPOHA

3. Please indicate your age category

18-25 26-33 34-41 42-49 50-57 58-65

4. Indicate your educational level

Secondary Diploma 1st Degree Advance Degree Professional
Qualification

5. Please indicate your job category

Controller Line Manager Team Leader Admin. Officer
Operative/floor staff

6. How long have you been working with your company?

Less than 1 year between one and four years more than four years

SECTION B: HEALTH AND SAFETY ISSUES IN YOUR ORGANISATION

This section uses a five-point Likert rating (1 to 5) to measure respondents' view on various health and safety issues in their respective company. This Likert scale is interpreted as “*Strongly Disagree*” for “1”; “*disagree somewhat*” for “2”; “*neutral*” for “3”; “*agree somewhat*” for “4”; and “*Strongly Agree*” for “5” respectively.

Please from “PART 1 to PART 5”, “*circle*” the number in the “*Likert rating*” that best describes your opinion.

PART 1: HEALTH AND SAFETY AS PART OF ORGANISATION'S LEADERHIP

<i>HEALTH AND SAFETY AS PART OF ORGANISATION'S LEADERHIP</i>					
		<i>Likert-rating</i>			
LD1	Leadership views organization's health and safety issues as share responsibility and not only the responsibilities of their subordinates or employees.	1	2	3	4
		5			
LD2	Leadership provides excellent health and safety policies.	1	2	3	4
		5			
LD3	Health and safety policies in my organization are well documented and are enforced.	1	2	3	4
		5			
LD4	Management view health and safety issues as part of organization's operations strategic direction.	1	2	3	4
		5			

PART 2: ORGANISATION'S SAFETY PROCEDURES

<i>ORGANISATION'S SAFETY PROCEDURES</i>					
		<i>Likert-rating</i>			
EK1	Employees always follow safe work procedures in my organization.	1	2	3	4
		5			
EK2	Employees always report safety incidents	1	2	3	4
		5			
EK3	Our company reviews and updates our safe work procedures regularly.	1	2	3	4
		5			

EK4	In my organization, employees are always involved in reviewing safe work procedures.	1	2	3	4	5
EK5	In my organization, safety procedures are review regularly.	1	2	3	4	5

P2-1. Which specific areas or operations in your organisation do you generally experienced accident?

.....
.....
.....

PART 3: TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT AND HEALTH & SAFETY ISSUE

<i>TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT AND HEALTH & SAFETY ISSUE</i>						
		<i>Likert-rating</i>				
TD1	All new employees are given induction training before they start work.	1	2	3	4	5
TD2	My organization has excellent training content which meet health and safety needs of the company.	1	2	3	4	5
TD3	Upon completion of safety training, employees are asked to provide feedbacks.	1	2	3	4	5
TD4	Our safety training is reviewed or updated if	1	2	3	4	5

	there is an incident.	5				
TD5	All employees get trained in safe work procedures for our jobs.	1	2	3	4	5

PART 4: ORGANISATION'S COMMITMENT TO HEALTH AND SAFETY ISSUES

<i>ORGANISATION'S COMMITMENT AND HEALTH AND SAFETY ISSUES</i>						
		<i>Likert-rating</i>				
OC1	My organization always provides personal protective clothing and equipment (PPE) to employees before the start work.	1	2	3	4	5
OC2	My organization has "no PPE no work" policy and are strictly enforced.	1	2	3	4	5
OC3	Front Line managers and supervisor make sure that works are done in a safely manner at all times.	1	2	3	4	5
OC4	Employees always report accident issues at the workplace.	1	2	3	4	5
OC5	Management always solves any health and safety problems that are reported.	1	2	3	4	5

PART 5: HEALTH AND SAFETY AND ORGNISATION'S PERFORMMNCE

<i>HEALTH AND SAFETY AND ORGNISATION'S PRODUCTIVITY</i>		<i>Likert-rating</i>				
P1	My organization is experiencing high absenteeism due to health and safety situation.	1	2	3	4	5
P2	My organization experience high breaks in operations due to frequent accidents at the workplace.	1	2	3	4	5
P3	Health and safety management system is part of the core drivers of my organization's performance	1	2	3	4	5

P5-1. In your view, recommend what need to be done to improve health and safety practices in your organisation.

.....

Tables for analysis

Health and safety and leadership Issues

Health and safety and leadership	Likert-Scale					Total Respondents
	1	2	3	4	5	
Leadership views organization's health and safety issues as share responsibility and not only the responsibilities of their subordinates or employees.	2	6	3	58	67	136
Leadership provides excellent health and safety policies.	10	12	6	50	58	136
Health and safety policies in my organization are	12	14	4	55	51	136

well documented and are enforced.						
Management view health and safety issues as part of organization's operations strategic direction.	7	9	7	53	60	136

Organisations safety procedures practices

Organisations safety procedures	Likert-Scale					Total Respondents
	1	2	3	4	5	
Employees always follow safe work procedures in my organization.	25	31	2	42	36	136
Employees always report safety incidents	37	33	8	28	30	136
Our company reviews and updates our safe work procedures regularly.	41	37	4	25	29	136

In my organization, employees are always involved in reviewing safe work procedures.	36	39	7	22	32	136
In my organization, safety procedures are review regularly.	40	28	3	26	39	136

HSE and training and development

HSE and training and development	Likert-Scale					Total Respondents
	1	2	3	4	5	
All new employees are given induction training before they start work.	2	9	0	55	70	136
My organization has excellent training content which meets health and safety needs of the company.	16	18	12	42	48	136
Upon completion of safety training, employees are asked to provide feedbacks.	37	39	12	22	26	136
Our safety training is	12	15	9	47	53	136

reviewed or updated if there

is an incident.

All employees get trained in	12	14	2	51	57	136
safe work procedures for						
our jobs.						

Organisation's commitment to HS issues

<i>Organisation's commitment to HS issues</i>	<i>Likert-Scale</i>					<i>Total Respondents</i>
	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	
My organization always provides personal protective clothing and equipment (PPE) to employees before the start work.	0	0	2	0	134	136
My organization has “no PPE no work” policy and are strictly enforced.	0	0	0	0	136	136
Front Line managers and supervisor make sure that works are done in a safely manner at all times.	8	5	4	53	66	136
Employees always report accident issues at the	37	33	8	28	30	136

workplace.

Management always solves 17 13 11 44 51 136
 any health and safety
 problems that are reported.

Health and safety and organisation's performance

Health and safety & organisation's performance	Likert-Scale					Total Respondents
	1	2	3	4	5	
My organization is experiencing high absenteeism due to health and safety situation.	52	41	16	11	16	136
My organization experience high breaks in operations due to frequent accidents at the workplace.	49	40	6	19	22	136
Health and safety management system is part of the core drivers of my organization's performance	9	6	2	55	64	136
